

UDK 615 (497.11)

ISSN 0004-1963 (Štampano izd.)
ISSN 2217-8767 (Online)

ARHIV ZA FARMACIJU

Godina 68

Broj 3

Beograd, 2018.

ČASOPIS SAVEZA FARMACEUTSKIH UDRUŽENJA SRBIJE

SPECIJALNI BROJ/SPECIAL ISSUE

VII Kongres farmaceuta Srbije sa međunarodnim učešćem

Zajedno stvaramo budućnost farmacije

Beograd, 10-14. oktobar 2018.

VII Serbian Congress of Pharmacy with international participation

Creating the future of pharmacy together

Belgrade, October 10-14, 2018

3/2018

PROPISIVANJE ANTIBIOTIKA U PRIMARNOJ ZDRAVSTVENOJ ZAŠTITI NA TERITORIJI NOVOG SADA: RAZLIKE IZMEĐU RECEPTA KOJE POKRIVA I NE POKRIVA ZDRAVSTVENO OSIGURANJE

**Nemanja Todorović¹, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹,
Boris Milijašević², Svetlana Goločorbin-Kon¹,
Nebojša Pavlović¹, Jelena Čanji¹, Katarina Jeremić¹**

¹Katedra za farmaciju, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu - Medicinski fakultet, ²Katedra za farmakologiju, toksikologiju i kliničku farmakologiju, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu - Medicinski fakultet (Srbija)

Praćenje propisivanja antibiotika je važno za smanjenje bakterijske rezistencije. Ovo istraživanje imalo je za cilj utvrđivanje razlika između propisivanja antibiotika preko receptata na teret fonda Republike Srbije (RFZO recepti) i onih receptata koji nisu na teretu fonda (ne-RFZO recepti).

Studija je retrospektivna, zasnovana na podacima dobijenim iz Z.U. Apoteka „Cvejić“ za januar 2018. Posmatrano je osam apoteka na teritoriji Novog Sada. Uzeti su podaci o propisivanju svih grupa antibiotika, uključujući i antibiotike za lokalnu primenu. Podaci su podeljeni u dve osnovne grupe: RFZO recepti i ne-RFZO recepti koje su dalje podeljene na sledeće varijable: pol, godine, ATC grupa, farmaceutski oblik i sedište proizvođača. Rezultati su izraženi kao broj izdatih antibiotika u okviru jedne kategorije varijable (n) i kao procenat od ukupnog broja propisanih antibiotika.

Tokom posmatranog perioda, od ukupnog broja izdatih i prodatih lekova (35.705) 8,47% su bili antibiotici (7,89% od svih RFZO receptata, 8,88% od prodaje lekova). Propisivanje antibiotika veće je putem ne-RFZO receptata (60,77%). Nijedan antibiotik iz ATC grupe A nije propisan o trošku fonda, iako se pojedini preparati ove grupe nalaze na listi A RFZO. Takođe, i antibiotici iz ATC grupa D, G, P i S su se manje propisivali putem RFZO receptata, u odnosu na ne-RFZO. ATC grupa J je najzastupljenija (94,10% RFZO antibiotskih receptata i 67,39% ne-RFZO). Najviše su se propisivali čvrsti farmaceutski oblici antibiotika (82,70%). Polučvrsti i tečni preparati antibiotika za lokalnu primenu su se više propisivali putem ne-RFZO receptata. Od svih propisanih antibiotika, 63,18% su bili antibiotici domaćih proizvođača.

Istraživanje je pokazalo veći procenat propisivanja antibiotika putem ne-RFZO receptata, posebno lokalnih polučvrstih i tečnih farmaceutskih oblika antibiotika. Rezultati sugerišu na neophodnost veće kontrole ove vrste propisivanja, kako sa stanovišta zdravstvenog osiguranja, tako i u opravdanosti upotrebe pojedinih grupa antibiotika.

PRESCRIBING OF ANTIBIOTICS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE IN NOVI SAD: DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PRESCRIPTIONS COVERED AND NOT COVERED BY HEALTH INSURANCE

**Nemanja Todorović¹, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹,
Boris Milijašević², Svetlana Goločorbin-Kon¹,
Nebojša Pavlović¹, Jelena Čanji¹, Katarina Jeremić¹**

¹Department of Pharmacy, University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Medicine,

²Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical pharmacology,
University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Medicine (Serbia)

The aim of this paper was to determine the differences between prescribing of antibiotics through prescriptions which are covered by the Fund of the Republic of Serbia (fund prescriptions-FP) and those prescription which are not covered by the Fund (non-fund prescriptions-NFP).

The study is retrospective, based on data obtained from Pharmacy "Cvejić" for January 2018. Eight pharmacies on the territory of Novi Sad were observed. Data on the prescription of all antibiotics was collected, including antibiotics for topical use. The data was divided into two basic groups: FP and NFP which are further divided into the following variables: gender, age, ATC group, pharmaceutical form and manufacturer. The results were expressed as the number of antibiotic drugs within one category of variables (n) and as a percentage of the total number of prescribed antibiotics.

During the observed period, of the total number of issued and sold drugs (35705), 8.47% were antibiotics (7.89% of all FP, 8.88% of sale drugs). Antibiotics were more often prescribed through NFP (60.77%). No antibiotic from ATC Group A was prescribed at the expense of the Fund. As for ATC groups D, G, P and S more antibiotics were prescribed through FP than NFP. ATC group J was the most commonly prescribed (94.10% of FP and 67.39% of NFP). Solid pharmaceutical forms of antibiotics were prescribed the most (82.70%). Semi-solid and liquid antibiotic preparations for topical use were more prescribed by NFP.

The study showed a higher percentage of antibiotic prescribed through NFP, especially semi-solid and liquid pharmaceutical forms for topical use. The results suggest the need for greater control of this type of prescription, both from the point of view of health insurance, and justification of the use of certain groups of antibiotics.